

The Importance of Minting and Keeping New PhDs in Artificial Intelligence

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20632300>

Author Note

Grace Ann Hansen has no known conflicts of interest to disclose. She corrects all her papers and articles with Grammarly, because even though she has deep thoughts, she has shallow patience for punctuation. She uses Anthropic's Claude in Research mode for source location and verification on cited factual claims. All interpretation, argument, and prose are her own. Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Grace Ann Hansen at grace@graceannhansen.com.

Abstract

This paper argues that minting and keeping a different kind of doctoral researcher in artificial intelligence (AI) is a public-interest necessity rather than a concession to a hype cycle. It addresses the grievances of writers and creators who regard generative AI as a vehicle for low-quality output and intellectual property theft as legitimate, then argues past the remedy of refusal on three grounds. First, the legitimacy of a grievance does not establish the efficacy of disengagement; the vindications creators have won came through litigation and bargaining. In rulings spanning 2025 and 2026, United States courts found that training on lawfully acquired works can constitute transformative fair use, while retaining pirated works does not, a distinction crystallized by the \$1.5 billion settlement in *Bartz v. Anthropic*. Second, the most consequential applications of AI lie far from internet slop, from the 2024 Nobel Prize in Chemistry for protein design to 1,451 AI-enabled medical devices authorized through 2025. Third, a threat landscape that includes the first documented AI-orchestrated cyber-espionage campaign, disclosed by Anthropic in November 2025, means disengagement shelters no one. The paper documents a pipeline crisis in which the industry produced more than 90% of notable frontier models in 2025, while the inflow of AI researchers to the United States collapsed. The remedy is to mint and keep researchers who are interdisciplinary, ethics-fluent, domain-embedded, and publicly accountable, and to fix the capture that diverts them. Recommendations tie public funding, regulatory alignment, dual appointments, public computing, and independent auditing to benchmarks.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, doctoral education, research pipeline, fair use, AI ethics, public-interest technology, AI for science, interpretability

The Importance of Minting and Keeping New PhDs in Artificial Intelligence

I have been called vile. I have been called despicable. The words came not from strangers but from fellow writers, people who share my craft and, I had assumed, my values, and they came because I chose to work with artificial intelligence and to pursue a doctorate in it. I record this not to solicit sympathy but to locate the argument that follows inside the conflict it means to address. I write this as someone standing on both sides of the line I am about to draw. I am a doctoral researcher in AI and a working fiction writer who publishes under several bylines, which places my creative output squarely within the market that generative systems are diluting. The hostility of writers and artists toward AI is not an abstraction to me, and neither is the injury that drives it. Any honest case for minting new AI doctorates must begin by conceding that the people most fluent in language, the people whose work I most admire and whose ranks I share, are among the technology's most committed adversaries, and that their reasons are not foolish.

The thesis of this paper is nonetheless that minting and keeping a different kind of AI doctoral researcher is a public-interest necessity rather than a concession to a hype cycle. Because AI is non-optional and dual-use, the question is not whether the work gets done but who does it, under whose ethics, and to whom it is answerable. A research pipeline captured by industry and abandoned by independent academia cannot serve healthcare, justice, science, or defense. The remedy is therefore twofold and inseparable. The first half is to mint more doctoral researchers of a particular kind: interdisciplinary, ethics-fluent, domain-embedded, and publicly accountable, with humanists and writers inside the room rather than protesting outside it. The second, equally important, half is to keep them, because the evidence assembled below shows that doctoral production is already growing. At the same time, the researchers it produces are being drawn into industry faster than they are minted. Volume without retention subsidizes the

very capture this paper deplures. The capture-fixing measures, public funding, public computing, dual appointments, independent auditing, and talent retention are not an appendix to the thesis.

They are the thesis.

Before the argument develops, the scale of the retention problem should be quantified at the outset, as it is the empirical heart of the case. By 2020, roughly 70% of new AI doctorates were taking industry jobs, up from about 21% in 2004 ([Ahmed et al., 2023](#)). Industry produced more than 90% of notable frontier models in 2025, and the inflow of AI researchers and developers to the United States fell 89% since 2017, with an 80% decline in the most recent year alone ([Stanford Institute for Human-Centered Artificial Intelligence \[Stanford HAI\], 2026](#)). A peer-reviewed analysis found that premier researchers' work tended to lose novelty and impact after they moved to industry ([Jurowetzki et al., 2025](#)). These are not the numbers of a field that needs only more bodies. They are the numbers of a field hemorrhaging its bodies, which is why the remedy must address both production and retention.

These two openings, the grievance and the thesis, are not in tension once their logic is made explicit. The grievance concerns what AI has done to a market for creative labor and to the dignity of authorship. The thesis concerns what AI is doing to medicine, mathematics, materials science, national security, and the structure of knowledge production itself. To hold both is to refuse two comfortable errors at once: the booster's error of treating criticism as Luddism, and the refusenik's error of treating disengagement as a strategy. The wager of this paper is that the writers who despise the technology are, in their grievance, frequently correct, and that their proposed remedy, refusal understood as disengagement, is nonetheless a mistake that will leave them and everyone else worse defended against the technology's genuine dangers.

This introduction advances three claims that the body of the paper defends in detail. The first is that the critics' factual claims about generative slop and intellectual-property appropriation are substantially accurate, and that the legal system has begun, unevenly, to vindicate parts of them while rejecting others. The second is that the largest problems to which AI is being applied, in healthcare, in the pursuit of justice, in the relief of poverty, in mathematics, and in the basic sciences, have nothing to do with AI music or the displacement of graphic artists, and that these problems are real, hard, and worth the most capable minds a society can train. The third is that the dangers of AI, arising from actors with different ethics, from hostile sovereign governments, from organized crime, and from lone hackers, are grave enough that the disdain of writers will not shield them, and that the only defense is more competent, ethically serious people working inside the field rather than fewer.

A word on the voice of this paper and the standing from which it speaks. I came to this argument not as a partisan of any laboratory but as a practitioner with a foot in two camps. Leading clinical analytics platforms at a large integrated health system taught me that the distance between a benchmark and a bedside is wide, that a model that performs well in a journal can fail a patient, and that the people who close that distance are not the ones who built the model but the ones who understood the clinic. Writing fiction for a living taught me what the creators are losing. That double vantage inclines me to a particular skepticism, aimed as readily at AI's promoters as at its detractors. I do not believe the marketing. I have also seen what a well-governed model can do for a tired clinician and a frightened patient, and I am unwilling to pretend the technology is only a machine for theft.

The paper proceeds in ten parts. It first takes the critics seriously, examining what the courts have actually said about training data and fair use. It then distinguishes three positions on

refusal, separating disengagement from the engaged refusal that has actually won creators their victories. It defends the inevitability premise against both the hype and the refusal. It surveys the problems worth a doctorate in science, medicine, and mathematics, including the harms that honesty requires acknowledging. It maps the threat landscape that makes opting out untenable. It documents the pipeline crisis in the research workforce. It describes the kind of scholars now needed. It sets out concrete on-ramps for creative professionals who will not pursue a doctorate but whose engagement the field needs. It draws out the policy and institutional implications, tying each to a benchmark that would change it. It concludes by returning to the grievance with which it began. Throughout, the discipline is the same: claims carry only as much weight as their sourcing supports, and where the evidence is contested or speculative, the paper says so.

Part 1. Taking the Critics Seriously: Slop, Theft, and What the Courts Actually Said

The case for new AI doctorates cannot be made by ignoring the objections of writers and artists. It must be made through them. This section grants the critics their strongest ground before contesting the conclusion they draw from it. There are two grievances, and they should be separated. The first is aesthetic and epistemic: that generative AI floods the information commons with low-quality, derivative output, the phenomenon now widely called slop. The second is moral and economic: that the models producing this output were built by copying creative work at an industrial scale without consent, credit, or compensation. The first grievance is real, but I will argue that it is a transitional nuisance. The second is the serious one, and it is the one on which the law has begun to speak.

The Slop Grievance and the Labor Grievance

The complaint about slop is that generative systems lower the cost of producing plausible text and images so dramatically that the commons fills with material that is fluent, confident, and frequently wrong or simply hollow. Writers experience this as a degradation of the environment in which they work. The complaint is accurate as far as it goes. But it is important to see what kind of complaint it is. It is a complaint about volume and about the economics of attention, not about the impossibility of value. The printing press, photography, and digital publishing each provoked structurally similar complaints, part of a documented cycle in which public alarm reincarnates with each new technology ([Orben, 2020](#)), and each lowered the floor while leaving room above it. The analogy has one limit worth naming: generative systems differ from earlier reproduction technologies in the near-zero marginal cost of output and in the feedback risk that synthetic text enters the corpora on which future models train. This does not make the present disruption painless. It does suggest that slop is a problem of curation and incentive rather than a permanent property of the technology, and that the people best positioned to solve it are those who understand both writing and machines.

The labor grievance is weightier and deserves to be stated at full strength. The objection is not that AI competes with human creativity in the abstract. It is that specific models were trained on copyrighted works without permission and are now deployed to generate substitutes that compete with the very works that trained them, returning nothing to their creators. Judge Vince Chhabria gave this objection its sharpest judicial articulation when he described the most promising theory available to authors: that a large language model can generate works similar enough in subject matter and genre that they will compete with the originals and indirectly substitute for them, a harm he called market dilution (*Kadrey v. Meta Platforms*, 2025). He observed that this dilution might not crowd out bestselling authors but could devastate lesser-

known and emerging writers facing artificial competition. That is the grievance, and it is not paranoia. It is an economic mechanism described by a federal judge, and as a working fiction writer among the lesser-known and emerging, I am inside the class he described.

The Fair-Use Triangle and the Cases That Define It

United States copyright law evaluates unlicensed uses under the four-factor fair-use test of Section 107: the purpose and character of the use, the nature of the copyrighted work, the amount and substantiality of the portion used, and the effect of the use on the market for the original. The AI training cases have turned overwhelmingly on the first and fourth factors, on transformativeness and market harm, and the rulings issued between 2025 and 2026 do not point in a single direction. They form a triangle of positions that any honest account must hold together.

The first vertex is *Thomson Reuters Enterprise Centre GmbH v. Ross Intelligence Inc.* (2025). On February 11, 2025, Judge Stephanos Bibas, sitting by designation in the District of Delaware, granted summary judgment to Thomson Reuters, holding that the legal-research startup Ross Intelligence had infringed copyright in 2,243 Westlaw headnotes used to train its AI search tool and rejecting Ross's fair-use defense as a matter of law. Judge Bibas found that Ross's use was not transformative because it served the same purpose as Westlaw and was built to compete directly with it, and that the fourth factor, market effect, favored Thomson Reuters. The decision expressly confined itself to non-generative AI, but it stands as the first substantive judicial rejection of a fair-use defense in the AI-training context, and it is now cited in nearly every subsequent case. The ruling is not final. Judge Bibas certified the fair-use and copyrightability questions for interlocutory appeal, finding substantial ground for difference of opinion on both, and the Third Circuit accepted the appeal in June 2025. In May 2026, the parties

completed a supplemental briefing on the circuit's own April 2026 decision in *American Society for Testing and Materials v. UpCodes, Inc.* (2026), which held at the preliminary-injunction stage that a startup's verbatim republication of technical standards incorporated into law was likely fair use, and oral argument is set for June 11, 2026. The appellate decision will be the first from any federal court of appeals on fair use in AI training; it may affirm, narrow, or vacate this vertex, and the triangle should be read as provisional until the Third Circuit rules. The lesson the critics draw from the district court's ruling is correct: there is no blanket immunity for training on copyrighted material.

The second vertex is *Bartz v. Anthropic* (2025). On June 23, 2025, Judge William Alsup of the Northern District of California ruled on summary judgment that Anthropic's use of lawfully acquired books to train its Claude models was "quintessentially transformative" (slip op. at 13) and therefore fair use, while simultaneously holding that downloading and retaining pirated copies from shadow libraries such as Library Genesis and Pirate Library Mirror was not fair use, calling the pirated copies "inherently, irredeemably infringing" (slip op. at 19). The case was filed by authors Andrea Bartz, Charles Graeber, and Kirk Wallace Johnson. The piracy exposure proved enormous. The parties reached a settlement that Judge Alsup preliminarily approved on September 25, 2025, after initially expressing misgivings and demanding a more rigorous claims process ([Association of American Publishers, 2025](#)). The settlement requires Anthropic to pay \$1.5 billion, approximately \$3,000 per work, for the nearly 500,000 books at issue, the largest copyright recovery in United States history ([Authors Guild, 2025](#)). A final fairness hearing proceeded before Judge Araceli Martínez-Olguín on May 14, 2026, with the motion taken under submission and final approval pending at this writing. The distinction the

case draws is the central fact of the present case law: how a model learns may be lawful even when the means by which its makers obtained the training data are not.

The third vertex is *Kadrey v. Meta Platforms* (2025). On June 25, 2025, two days after *Bartz*, Judge Chhabria granted Meta summary judgment on the authors' claim that training the Llama models on their books infringed copyright. But the ruling was narrow and openly reluctant. Judge Chhabria held that the thirteen plaintiff authors, including Richard Kadrey and Sarah Silverman, had simply failed to develop a record on the market-dilution theory that he considered most promising. He wrote that his decision "does not stand for the proposition that Meta's use of copyrighted materials to train its language models is lawful," but only "that these plaintiffs made the wrong arguments and failed to develop a record in support of the right one" (*Kadrey v. Meta Platforms*, 2025, slip op. at 5). He went further, stating that "in many circumstances it will be illegal to copy copyright-protected works to train generative AI models without permission," and that to avoid liability, companies "will generally need to pay copyright holders for the right to use their materials" (slip op. at 4). This is a decision nominally for the AI company that, in its reasoning, reads like a brief for the next plaintiff.

Two further matters complete the triangle. In the consolidated *In re OpenAI* litigation in the Southern District of New York, the New York Times and other publishers and authors have pressed claims that OpenAI and Microsoft copied millions of articles to train ChatGPT, claims now consolidated as *In re OpenAI, Inc. Copyright Infringement Litigation*. Judge Sidney Stein declined in March 2025 to dismiss the core infringement claims, allowing the case to proceed. In January 2026, he affirmed a magistrate's order compelling OpenAI to produce a sample of 20 million anonymized ChatGPT logs over the company's privacy objections, on the ground that the logs bear on OpenAI's fair-use defense and the question of market substitution. As of mid-2026,

the case remains in discovery, with summary-judgment briefing anticipated. The outcome is genuinely uncertain, and it would be inaccurate to claim that the industry has prevailed.

The *Getty Images v. Stability AI* litigation shows how jurisdiction shapes outcome (*Getty Images (US) Inc. v. Stability AI Ltd.*, 2025). On November 4, 2025, the High Court of England and Wales handed down its judgment. Getty had abandoned its primary copyright and database claims during trial because it could not establish that the training of Stable Diffusion occurred in the United Kingdom, leaving a secondary-infringement claim and a trademark claim. The court rejected the secondary-infringement claim, holding that Stable Diffusion's model weights are not an infringing copy because they do not store or reproduce the training images, while finding limited and historic trademark infringement where Getty watermarks appeared in some outputs. The ruling decided little about whether training itself infringes, leaving that question for the parallel United States proceeding and for legislation. Earlier AI-training disputes elsewhere in Europe have produced different results, underscoring that the global legal position is fragmented rather than settled.

The Licensing-Market Response

The most important development for the labor grievance is not in the courtrooms but in the contracts. The very fragmentation and uncertainty of the case law have created powerful incentives to license rather than litigate, and a market for training content is emerging. Judge Chhabria's opinion records that Meta's head of generative AI discussed spending up to \$100 million on licensing before negotiations foundered, not on price but on the fragmentation of rights, because publishers generally do not hold the subsidiary rights to license books for AI training, and there is no organization for collective licensing of such rights (*Kadrey v. Meta Platforms*, 2025). That observation identifies both a market and its central obstacle. On the

publisher side, several news organizations have concluded licensing agreements with AI companies, including The New York Times's multiyear agreement with Amazon, its first with an AI company (Fischer, 2025), a development that turns the grievance into a negotiation. The existence of these deals matters to this paper's argument for a specific reason: it demonstrates that the choice is not between theft and abstention. There is a third path, licensed and compensated use, and building it requires people who understand contracts, copyright, the technical realities of training, and the working lives of creators. That is a job for trained researchers, not for refuseniks.

The honest conclusion of this section is that the critics are substantially right about the harm and substantially wrong about the remedy. The courts have confirmed that piracy is not fair use, that market dilution is a live and possibly decisive theory, and that the law will likely require payment in many circumstances. None of this was secured by writers refusing to engage with the technology. It was secured by litigators, scholars, and technologists who engaged with it intimately enough to articulate the harm in terms a court could act on. The grievance is the beginning of the argument for more AI doctorates, not against them, because the people who will build the licensed, accountable, creator-respecting systems of the future must first be trained to understand the systems that exist.

Part 2. Three Positions on Refusal

The argument of this paper is often heard as a demand that writers stop refusing and start cooperating, as though the only choice were between embrace and rejection. That framing is too coarse, and the paper's own evidence dissolves it. The victories celebrated in the previous section were not won through cooperation with industry. They were won by people who refused industry's terms and fought, in court and at the bargaining table. Refusal, properly understood, is

not one thing. It is at least three, and the distinctions matter because the paper endorses two of them and faults only the third.

The first position is refusal as avoidance. Here, the creator regards AI as nothing but a dangerous enemy and declines to deal with the fallout around their own craft, or with its defense, by any means other than turning away. This is the stance that treats engagement as contamination, that reads any contact with the technology as complicity, and that confines its response to condemnation. It is the position from which the judgment quoted at the outset was delivered. It is understandable as a reaction to real injury, but as a strategy, it forfeits everything and secures nothing.

The second position is refusal as a form of litigation. Here, the creator is not personally involved in building or using AI but instead defends their work and rights by navigating the legal system and advancing the field's ethics and practices, rather than letting them stagnate. The plaintiff-authors in *Bartz* and *Kadrey*, the publishers in the OpenAI litigation, and Getty in the United Kingdom all occupy this position. They refused to consent, and they made their refusal expensive and consequential. The \$1.5 billion *Bartz* settlement and Judge Chhabria's market-dilution analysis are products of this refusal, not of cooperation. The 2023 Writers Guild of America strike belongs here as well: through collective refusal to work, the guild secured contractual protections governing the use of AI in screenwriting, protections no individual writer could have won by avoidance ([Writers Guild of America, 2023](#)). This is engagement by adversarial means, and it has a win record.

The third position is the refusal of harm from inside. Here, the participant works within the AI revolution as an ethical gatekeeper and a developer of policy and practice that minimizes harm, fully engaged with the technology precisely to constrain it. This is the position the bulk of

this paper argues for, and it is the position doctoral training is meant to produce. It refuses the technology's worst uses not by standing apart from it but by occupying the rooms where its uses are decided.

The paper endorses the second and third positions without reservation and confines its critique to the first. The litigant and the inside reformer are both engaged; they differ only in the venue of their engagement, the courtroom or the laboratory. What avoidance forfeits is not the moral high ground, which it may well keep, but any capacity to shape the outcome. The hostile state, the criminal syndicate, and the careless deployer do not pause for anyone's disapproval. A refusal that consists only of disapproval leaves the field to them. The distinction this section draws is therefore not between the brave and the timid but between forms of refusal that change the world and a form that merely registers an objection to it.

Part 3. The Inevitability Premise: Why Refusal as Avoidance Fails

The argument that creators should engage with AI rather than avoid it depends on a premise that deserves scrutiny rather than assertion: that AI is here to stay regardless of anyone's approval. This premise is easy to state and easy to abuse. Stated carelessly, it becomes the booster's slogan, used to shame skeptics and to wave away every concern as obsolete. Stated carefully, it is a claim about the joint weight of two bodies of evidence, the evidence of hype and the evidence of capability, neither of which can be ignored. This section examines both, because a premise worth relying on must survive its own counterevidence.

The Case for a Bubble

There is substantial reason to believe that the AI sector exhibits the classic features of a financial bubble, and intellectual honesty requires confronting it directly rather than burying it.

The most-cited data point comes from the Massachusetts Institute of Technology's Project NANDA, whose 2025 report, *The GenAI Divide: State of AI in Business 2025*, found that roughly 95% of enterprise generative AI pilots delivered no measurable impact on profit and loss ([Challapally et al., 2025](#); [Estrada, 2025](#)). The report, based on structured interviews with representatives from 52 organizations, survey responses from 153 senior leaders, and a systematic review of more than 300 publicly disclosed AI initiatives, attributed the failures not to model quality but to a learning gap in organizational integration. The figure has been criticized for a short six-month measurement window and for relying on interviews rather than audited financials, and those criticisms are fair. But even discounted, a 95% pilot failure rate against tens of billions of dollars in enterprise spending is a serious indictment of the gap between the technology's promise and its present return.

The skepticism extends to the principals. Sam Altman, the chief executive of OpenAI, has himself acknowledged the bubble dynamics, asking whether investors as a whole are overexcited about AI and answering that, in his opinion, they are ([Nolan, 2025b](#)). The financing structures reinforce the worry. Through 2025, a series of large, interlocking deals among Nvidia, OpenAI, Oracle, AMD, and cloud providers such as CoreWeave drew sustained attention to the risk of circular financing, in which a chip maker invests in a model developer that in turn commits to buying that maker's chips or renting cloud capacity from a third party the chip maker also funds. The concern, articulated by financial journalists and economists, is twofold: that such arrangements can inflate apparent revenue through round-tripping, and that they concentrate systemic risk so that the failure of one node could cascade ([Bloomberg News, 2026](#)). Capital expenditure on data centers has reached the point at which the four largest cloud providers each plan to spend above \$100 billion annually, roughly \$725 billion combined for 2026 ([James,](#)

[2026](#)), and the International Energy Agency projected that electricity demand from data centers would more than double by 2030, to around 945 terawatt-hours, from roughly 415 terawatt-hours in 2024 ([International Energy Agency, 2025](#)). A technology that consumes power and capital on this scale, while most corporate pilots fail to show returns, is a technology with bubble exposure. To deny this would be to commit exactly the error of credulity that this paper warns against.

The Case for Capability

And yet the bubble evidence does not establish that AI will recede, any more than the dot-com bubble's collapse meant the internet was a fad. The dot-com analogy is precise and instructive. The late-1990s internet bubble was genuine; enormous sums were destroyed when it burst. The internet was also simultaneously the most important infrastructural technology of its generation. Both things were true. Altman's own framing invokes this history: bubbles form when smart people get overexcited about a kernel of truth, and the kernel of truth here is large. The capability evidence, drawn from the Stanford Institute for Human-Centered Artificial Intelligence's 2026 AI Index Report, is difficult to reconcile with the view that AI is principally vapor ([Stanford HAI, 2026](#)).

Consider adoption. The 2026 AI Index found that generative AI reached 53% population-level adoption within three years of its mass-market introduction, faster than either the personal computer or the internet over comparable periods, and that organizational adoption reached 88% of surveyed companies ([Stanford HAI, 2026](#)). The estimated consumer surplus from generative-AI tools in the United States reached \$172 billion annually by early 2026, up from \$112 billion a year earlier, with the median value per user tripling. Consider capability. On the SWE-bench Verified software-engineering benchmark, in which systems resolve verified real-world software issues, performance rose from roughly 60% to near 100% of the human baseline in a single year.

On Humanity's Last Exam, a benchmark of expert-level questions designed to favor human experts, top-model accuracy increased by roughly 30 percentage points in a single year, from a baseline of 8.8%. Frontier models now meet or exceed human performance on doctoral-level science questions and competition mathematics. These are not marketing claims; they are measured results from an independent academic index, and they describe a rate of capability improvement that is incompatible with imminent disappearance.

The reconciliation of the two bodies of evidence is straightforward once stated. A sector can be financially overvalued and technologically consequential at the same time. The bubble, if it bursts, will destroy capital and reorder the industry; it will not delete the trained models, the trained people, or the demonstrated capabilities. After the dot-com crash, the internet did not vanish; it consolidated and grew. The reasonable expectation for AI is the same: a painful financial correction is plausible, even likely, and the underlying technology will nonetheless persist and deepen. For the creator, deciding whether to engage is the decisive point. One does not get to wait out a bubble and emerge into a world without AI. One emerges into a world in which AI is more entrenched, the financial froth is gone, and the institutions that govern the technology have been built by whoever showed up.

The Reality of Creative Displacement

The inevitability premise has a hard edge that the argument must not soften, because softening it would betray the very critics the paper takes seriously. The 2026 AI Index documented the first concrete evidence of AI-driven workforce displacement rather than a mere forecast, concentrated at the entry level, with employment among United States software developers aged 22 to 25 falling nearly 20% since 2022 ([Stanford HAI, 2026](#)). The displacement pressure on creative workers is real and is already producing lost income for illustrators,

copywriters, translators, and voice actors. This is the labor grievance of the earlier section, now visible in employment data. The point of insisting on the inevitability premise is not to tell displaced workers that their loss is acceptable. It is to insist that avoidance does not reverse the displacement; it only removes the displaced from the conversation about what comes next, including discussions of retraining, licensing, redistribution, and the design of systems that complement rather than replace human work. The choice to automate tasks that complement humans rather than those that replace them is made by the people in the room.

Part 4. Problems Worth a Doctorate: Science, Medicine, Mathematics, and the Public Interest

If AI were only a machine for generating marketing copy and imitation art, the grievances of the previous sections would more or less exhaust the subject, and a thoughtful person might reasonably conclude that the technology was not worth a life's work. The premise of this paper is that this picture is radically incomplete. The applications of AI that justify the training of new doctoral researchers have, for the most part, nothing to do with internet slop, AI music, or the displacement of graphic artists. They concern the folding of proteins, the control of fusion plasma, the discovery of materials, the proof of theorems, the forecasting of weather, the discovery of drugs, and the practice of medicine. This section surveys these, and because the case must be honest, it gives equal attention to the documented harms that accompany them.

Protein Folding and the Nobel Recognition

The clearest demonstration that AI has become a tool of fundamental science is the 2024 Nobel Prize in Chemistry ([Nobel Prize Outreach, 2024](#)). Half the prize went to David Baker for computational protein design; the other half jointly to Demis Hassabis and John Jumper of

Google DeepMind for protein structure prediction. AlphaFold2, the system that Hassabis and Jumper built, predicted the three-dimensional structures of virtually all of the roughly 200 million proteins cataloged by science, solving in substantial part a problem that had resisted biology for half a century, the problem of predicting how a protein's amino-acid sequence determines the shape on which its function depends. By the time of the award, the AlphaFold database had been used by more than two million researchers across more than 190 countries ([Nobel Prize Outreach, 2024](#)). This is not a productivity tool. It is a contribution to basic science of the kind that wins the highest honor the discipline confers, and it was made by people with doctoral-level training who chose to apply machine learning to a biological problem.

Materials, Fusion, and Weather

The protein result is not isolated, though it is the most decorated. In materials science, Google DeepMind's Graph Networks for Materials Exploration, or GNoME, predicted 2.2 million new crystal structures, of which approximately 380,000 were identified as stable candidates for synthesis, a result the company described as an order-of-magnitude expansion in stable materials known to humanity, with more than 700 of the structures independently synthesized in concurrent work ([Merchant et al., 2023](#)). Here, the paper must exercise the discipline it preaches, because the GNoME result drew a substantive peer critique. Cheetham and Seshadri (2024) argued that the predictions were crystalline inorganic compounds rather than useful materials in the fuller sense, that a random sample of the proposed structures failed a three-part test of credibility, novelty, and usefulness, and that many were trivial modifications of known compounds. The honest reading is that GNoME demonstrated a powerful method that generated an enormous, unfiltered space of candidates whose practical value requires the focused judgment of experimental materials scientists. That conclusion does not diminish the case for AI

doctorates; it strengthens it, because it shows that the technology produces results that only trained domain experts can properly evaluate.

In fusion energy, Degraeve et al. (2022) reported that a deep reinforcement learning controller developed by DeepMind and the Swiss Plasma Center at the École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne successfully shaped and maintained plasma configurations in the TCV tokamak, controlling the magnetic coils directly and replacing a nested control architecture with a single learned controller. Controlling plasma at temperatures hotter than the sun's core is among the hardest control problems in physics, and a learned system did so on a real machine rather than only in simulation. In weather forecasting, Lam et al. (2023) reported that GraphCast significantly outperformed the most accurate operational deterministic system, the European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts' HRES, on 90.3% of 1,380 verification targets, and on 99.7% of targets within the troposphere, while producing forecasts in minutes rather than hours.

Mathematics

Perhaps the most striking recent results are in mathematics, long considered the redoubt of irreducibly human insight. In 2024, DeepMind's AlphaProof and AlphaGeometry 2 systems reached a silver-medal standard at the International Mathematical Olympiad, solving four of six problems for 28 points. However, the systems required human translation of problems into formal languages such as Lean and took up to three days of computation ([Google DeepMind, 2024](#)). In 2025, an advanced version of Gemini equipped with the Deep Think reasoning mode reached gold-medal standard, solving five of six problems for 35 points, operating end-to-end in natural language directly from the official problem statements and finishing within the 4.5-hour competition limit, with results graded and certified by the official IMO coordinators ([Google](#)

[DeepMind, 2025a](#)). The progression from silver to gold in a single year and the elimination of the manual translation bottleneck mark a qualitative advance in machine reasoning. DeepMind's AlphaEvolve method was separately applied to more than 50 open problems in mathematical analysis, geometry, combinatorics, and number theory and improved the best known solutions in roughly 20% of them, and it discovered a more efficient method for matrix multiplication, a core computational operation ([Google DeepMind, 2025b](#)). These are contributions to mathematics, made by machines, supervised by people trained to understand them. A reader will notice that every flagship result in this survey so far issues from a single industrial laboratory, and the concentration is not an accident of selection. It is the compute divide made visible, and it is itself evidence for the pipeline argument this paper makes: when only one class of institution can afford frontier science, even a survey of triumphs reads as a symptom.

Medicine

For a researcher who came to AI through clinical analytics, the medical applications are the most concrete. The Food and Drug Administration had authorized 1,451 AI-enabled medical devices through the end of 2025, of which 1,104, or 76%, were in radiology, with GE HealthCare leading at 120 authorizations ([Stanford HAI, 2026](#); [U.S. Food and Drug Administration, 2025](#)). Ambient documentation tools that automatically draft clinical notes from patient visits saw widespread adoption in 2025; in a multicenter study of 263 clinicians across six health systems, 30 days with an ambient scribe was associated with a decline in clinician burnout from 51.9% to 38.8% and with significant reductions in after-hours documentation time ([Olson et al., 2025](#)). Clinical decision support, triage, and image analysis are moving from pilot to practice. But here, more than anywhere, the discipline of honesty is essential, and the 2026 AI Index offers a cautionary note: a review of more than 500 clinical AI studies found that nearly

half relied on exam-style questions rather than real patient data. Only 5% used real clinical data ([Stanford HAI, 2026](#)). The evidence base for clinical AI is thinner than the deployment rate suggests. That gap between benchmark and bedside is exactly the gap I watched practitioners struggle to close, and it is precisely the kind of problem that requires researchers trained in both informatics and the realities of care.

The Documented Harms

A paper that listed only triumphs would be a brochure, not an argument. The same technologies that fold proteins also encode and magnify human injustice, and the case for more AI doctorates rests in part on the need for researchers equipped to find and fix these harms. The harms are documented. In criminal justice, the COMPAS recidivism-risk tool was shown to produce racially disparate error rates, flagging Black defendants as future criminals at higher false-positive rates than white defendants ([Angwin et al., 2016](#)). Predictive-policing systems have been criticized for entrenching the biases of the historical arrest data on which they are trained, directing scrutiny back to the communities already over-policed ([Lum & Isaac, 2016](#)). The most devastating documented case is the Dutch childcare-benefits scandal, the toeslagenaffaire, in which the tax authority's risk-classification system wrongly accused approximately 26,000 parents of benefit fraud in the 2005 to 2019 window, with later official tallies running higher, used nationality as a risk factor in a manner Amnesty International characterized as racial profiling, drove families into financial ruin, and contributed to the resignation of the third Rutte cabinet on January 15, 2021 ([Amnesty International, 2021](#)). These are not hypothetical risks. They are realized harms, with names and victims, produced by automated systems deployed without adequate scrutiny. The lesson is not that AI should be abandoned to those who would deploy it carelessly. It is that the field urgently needs more

researchers whose training makes them capable of auditing, contesting, and correcting such systems, and whose ethics make them willing to do so.

Part 5. The Threat Landscape: Why Opting Out Offers No Shelter

The argument so far has shown that AI is entrenched and being applied to problems of the first importance. This section establishes the proposition that moves avoidance from ineffective to dangerous: that AI is dual-use, already in the hands of actors with hostile intent and different ethics, and that the disdain of any individual or profession will not shield them from its effects. The writer who refuses to engage with AI does not thereby become invisible to the state-sponsored hacker, the disinformation operation, or the AI-enabled fraud. The threat is indifferent to disapproval.

State-Sponsored AI-Orchestrated Attack

The watershed event is recent and specific. On November 13, 2025, Anthropic disclosed what it assessed with high confidence to be the first documented case of a large-scale cyberattack executed largely without human intervention ([Anthropic, 2025b](#)). The company attributed the operation, designated GTG-1002, to a Chinese state-sponsored group that manipulated Anthropic's Claude Code tool to attempt infiltration of roughly 30 global targets, including large technology companies, financial institutions, chemical manufacturers, and government agencies, succeeding in a small number of cases. According to Anthropic's account, the AI executed an estimated 80% to 90% of the tactical work, autonomously conducting reconnaissance, generating exploit code, harvesting credentials, moving laterally, and exfiltrating data across six structured phases, with human operators intervening only at a handful of strategic decision points, for as little as a few minutes per phase. The attackers bypassed Claude's safety guardrails through

social engineering, convincing the model that it was performing authorized defensive security testing, which was decomposed into innocuous-seeming subtasks. The disclosure prompted a request from the United States House Committee on Homeland Security for Anthropic's chief executive to testify. The significance is not that a new attack technique was invented but that the cost structure of sophisticated cyber operations collapsed: an adversary achieved nation-state operational scale while investing a fraction of the usual human effort. Independent corroboration of the vendor's attribution remained limited, and Anthropic itself noted that Claude's hallucinations imposed real limits on the attack's reliability, so the claim should be read as a high-confidence vendor disclosure rather than a fully independently verified forensic finding. Even so discounted, it marks a threshold.

AI-Integrated Malware and the Adversarial-Misuse Reports

The GTG-1002 disclosure did not arrive without warning. The Google Threat Intelligence Group, building on its January 2025 report on the adversarial misuse of generative AI, published findings in November 2025 documenting the first identified malware families that use large language models during execution rather than merely in development ([Google Threat Intelligence Group, 2025](#)). One, tracked as PROMPTFLUX, queries the Gemini API to rewrite and obfuscate its own code to evade signature-based detection. Another, PROMPTSTEAL, attributed to the Russian state-backed actor APT28 and reported by Ukraine's CERT-UA as LAMEHUG, queries a model to generate system commands dynamically rather than hard-coding them, while masquerading as an image-generation tool. The same body of reporting documented state-sponsored actors from China, Iran, North Korea, and Russia misusing Gemini across the stages of their operations, from reconnaissance and phishing-lure creation to malware development and data exfiltration, frequently bypassing guardrails through pretextual framing

such as posing as participants in capture-the-flag security exercises. These are not projections. They are documented incidents reported by the security teams of major technology companies.

Deepfakes, Disinformation, and CBRN Concerns

Beyond intrusion lie the threats to the information environment and to physical safety. AI-generated deepfakes and synthetic media have been deployed in election and disinformation contexts across 2024 to 2026, sufficiently to prompt regulatory response, including a prohibition on AI systems that generate non-consensual intimate imagery and child sexual abuse material, provisionally agreed in the European Union's May 2026 AI Act amendments and awaiting formal adoption at this writing ([Council of the European Union, 2026](#)). AI-driven data breaches and fraud have grown as the technology lowers the cost of credible deception at scale. And the frontier laboratories have themselves begun publishing evaluations of whether their models provide uplift to actors seeking chemical, biological, radiological, or nuclear capabilities, a category of risk grave enough that the companies treat it as a gating concern for deployment ([Anthropic, 2025a](#)). The existence of these evaluations is itself evidence that the dual-use risk is taken seriously by those closest to the technology.

The Defensive Counterpoint

The threat landscape is not one-sided, and the same disclosures that document the danger also document the defense. Anthropic detected and disrupted the GTG-1002 campaign using its own monitoring, banned the relevant accounts, and shared intelligence with authorities and industry partners ([Anthropic, 2025b](#)). Google's threat-intelligence work both identifies AI-enabled malware and feeds defensive countermeasures ([Google Threat Intelligence Group, 2025](#)). AI is increasingly used to detect intrusions at machine speed, to triage vulnerabilities, and

to disrupt attacks that human-paced defenses cannot match. This defensive counterpoint is the hinge of the entire argument. If AI-enabled attacks can be countered only by AI-enabled defenses, then the supply of competent, ethically serious defenders is a matter of collective security. Every capable researcher who refuses the field on principle is one fewer defender, and the attackers face no such scruple. The writer's disdain for AI is, in this light, not a moral stand that the hostile state will respect. It is a unilateral disarmament that the hostile state will exploit.

Part 6. The Pipeline Crisis: Who Is Left to Do the Research

If the preceding sections establish that AI is entrenched, consequential, and dangerous, this section establishes the problem that gives the paper its urgency: the research pipeline that should produce independent, publicly accountable researchers is being hollowed out by industry, and the question of who is left to do the research has become acute. The evidence is now substantial and, in places, peer-reviewed.

The Migration Literature

The foundational finding comes from Ahmed et al. (2023). They documented that industry has come to dominate the three inputs of modern AI research, computing power, large datasets, and skilled researchers, and that this dominance translates into research outputs. Their most cited statistic is the talent shift: the share of new AI doctorates taking industry jobs rose from roughly 21% in 2004 to nearly 70% in 2020, a transition far faster than in most scientific fields. On the output side, they found that the largest AI models came from industry 96% of the time and from leading benchmarks 91% of the time, while industry models were, on average, 29 times larger than academic ones, a direct reflection of the compute divide. Their warning was

explicit: this concentration should worry policymakers because public-interest alternatives for important AI tools may disappear.

A 2025 peer-reviewed study sharpened the concern by focusing on consequences. Jurowetzki et al. (2025) analyzed OpenAlex data covering large bodies of papers and authors. They found a significant transition of premier talent to industry over the past decade, with young, highly cited scholars from leading institutions most likely to move. Critically, they found that after the transition, these researchers' work tended to show reduced novelty and impact. This is the finding that should alarm anyone who cares about the long-run health of the field: the move to industry does not merely relocate talent, it appears to redirect it away from the exploratory, high-novelty research that academic freedom is supposed to protect, toward work with immediate commercial application. The brain drain runs deeper than headcount.

The Compensation Gap and the Compute Divide

The mechanism driving the migration is not mysterious. The compensation differential is enormous. Reporting in *Fortune* in June 2025 documented that newly minted AI doctorates were commanding six- and seven-figure packages, with industry compensation reaching multiples of typical faculty pay, against an American Association of University Professors figure for the 2023-2024 average full-professor salary in the range of \$155,000 ([Quinn, 2024](#); [Sternlicht, 2025](#)). At the extreme, frontier laboratories and the largest technology companies have reportedly offered individual packages worth tens of millions of dollars (Nolan, 2025a), sums no university can match. Layered on top of pay is the compute divide. Training a competitive frontier model can cost tens to hundreds of millions of dollars in computation, a scale that even the wealthiest universities cannot sustain. In contrast, industry models dwarf academic ones in size. A doctoral student who wishes to work at the frontier of model capability often cannot do

so within a university at all because the university lacks the necessary machines. The pull of money and the push of inadequate infrastructure operate together. This is the crux of why minting alone is not enough: a doctorate produced and then drawn straight into industry has been minted, not kept, and the public-interest pipeline is no better off for it.

The National Numbers and the Counter-Trend

The aggregate picture confirms the individual one. The 2026 AI Index found that industry produced more than 90% of notable frontier models in 2025, and that the inflow of AI researchers and developers to the United States fell 89% since 2017, with an 80% decline in the most recent year alone, even as the United States led the world in private AI investment at \$285.9 billion in 2025, roughly 23 times China's \$12.4 billion ([Stanford HAI, 2026](#)). That figure measures migration, the count of AI researchers and developers moving into the country, drawn from the Zeki talent-tracking dataset on which the Index relies. It belongs in a capture argument because it shrinks the pool from which academia and the public-interest sector recruit, compounding the documented diversion, and because its near-term driver is visa and immigration policy as much as industry demand. The supply of new doctorates, meanwhile, has grown but not nearly fast enough to offset the diversion to industry, and the proportion entering academia continued to shrink for much of the period.

There is, however, one genuinely encouraging counter-trend, and intellectual honesty requires giving it equal prominence. According to the 2026 AI Index, after years of decline, the academic share of new AI doctorates rose recently, and the industry share of new AI PhDs in the United States fell from 77% in 2022 toward a lower figure in 2024, with the academic share rising correspondingly ([Stanford HAI, 2026](#)). New AI doctorates awarded across the United States and Canada, as counted in the Computing Research Association's Taulbee Survey, rose

22% between 2022 and 2024. These figures suggest that the pipeline is not collapsing uniformly and that, under the right conditions, the academic share can recover. The policy question is how to make that recovery durable, and the public infrastructure to support it is beginning to appear: the National AI Research Resource pilot, launched by the National Science Foundation in January 2024, has grown to support a large and expanding number of research projects and thousands of students across the country, backed by a coalition of federal agencies and private partners ([National Science Foundation, 2024](#)). The counter-trend is fragile and contingent, but it is real and the empirical ground for hope. It is also the direct evidence for this paper's central structural claim: because production is already rising while retention is not, the decisive lever is keeping.

Part 7. What Kind of Academics, Researchers, and Professors Do We Now Need

Establishing that more doctoral researchers are needed does not by itself answer the harder question of what kind. The thesis of this paper is emphatic on this point: the remedy is a different kind of researcher, one trained across disciplines, fluent in the ethics of the systems they build, embedded in the domains where AI does its work, and accountable to the public, with humanists and writers at the table rather than at the barricade. This section specifies what that means in concrete terms of training and scholarship.

Interdisciplinary and Ethics-Integrated Training

The default model of doctoral training in machine learning produces narrow technical excellence: a researcher who can advance a benchmark but has not been trained to ask whether the benchmark measures anything that matters or to consider whom the resulting system will harm. The harms documented earlier, the COMPAS disparities, the predictive-policing feedback

loops, and the Dutch benefits catastrophe were not failures of technical skill. They were failures of judgment, context, and ethical foresight, of exactly the faculties that narrow technical training neglects. The doctoral programs require integrating ethics not as a single required course but as a thread running through the technical curriculum, so that the question of harm is asked at the design stage rather than after deployment. They are interdisciplinary by construction, pairing machine learning with law, medicine, public policy, sociology, or the humanities, because the consequential applications of AI are all applications to some domain, and a researcher ignorant of the domain cannot anticipate its failure modes.

Domain Embedding

The case for domain embedding is the case I know best from practice. A model that performs well on a medical benchmark may fail in a clinic because the clinic's data differ from the training data. After all, clinicians do not use the tool as designed, or because the optimized metric was not the one that matters to patients. Closing the gap between benchmark and bedside, or between benchmark and courtroom, or between benchmark and classroom, requires researchers embedded in the domain who understand its workflows, incentives, and people. The 2026 AI Index finding that only 5% of clinical AI studies used real clinical data is a direct symptom of insufficient domain embedding ([Stanford HAI, 2026](#)). The doctoral researcher the field needs in medicine is not a machine-learning specialist who occasionally consults a doctor, but someone trained at the intersection, fluent in both.

Alignment, Interpretability, and Independent Auditing as Scholarly Fields

Two relatively young technical fields deserve recognition as scholarly disciplines central to the public interest. AI alignment studies how to ensure that increasingly capable systems

pursue intended goals, and interpretability studies how to understand the internal mechanisms by which models produce their outputs, opening the black box enough to predict and control behavior. These are not engineering afterthoughts; they are deep scientific problems, and they are the problems on which the safety of advanced systems most directly depends. A research ecosystem in which alignment and interpretability are pursued only within the companies building the most powerful models is a structural conflict of interest, because the body marking its own homework has every incentive to grade gently. The remedy is independent academic capacity for research on alignment and interpretability, and, beyond that, independent auditing of frontier models by researchers outside the companies that build them. The Getty and OpenAI litigation showed how much turns on understanding what a model actually does internally; independent interpretability research is the scholarly foundation for that understanding.

The Teaching Multiplier

There is a further reason the academic share matters more than headcount, and it compounds over generations. A doctoral researcher produces research and trains the next cohort. Every academic drawn into industry is therefore subtracted twice: once as a researcher who will now do proprietary rather than public-interest work, and again as a teacher who will now not train the students who would have followed. The brain drain is not a one-time transfer of stock; it is a recurring loss of the flow, because the captured professor's unwritten students never enter the pipeline at all. This is the strongest reason the paper's remedy centers on keeping. A retained academic seeds a lineage; a lost one ends it. Any honest accounting of the pipeline crisis must price in the unborn cohorts, and that accounting makes the academic share the variable to watch.

The Role of the Humanities and Writers

Here, the paper returns to the writers with whom it began and makes its central constructive claim about them. The humanities are not a decorative addition to AI research; they are load-bearing. The questions that AI forces, what counts as authorship, what we owe to those whose work trains a model, how to describe a capability honestly, what a just distribution of the technology's gains would look like, and what it means for a machine to reason, are humanistic questions. They are answered badly when answered only by technologists. Writers in particular possess a specific and scarce skill that the field needs: the discipline of precise language, the ability to distinguish a research program from a promise, speculation from fraud, a benchmark from a bedside. The slop that writers rightly despise is, in part, a failure of exactly this discipline. The remedy for slop is not the absence of writers from AI but their presence within it, shaping the standards by which output is judged and the language in which capabilities are described. A writer inside the room is worth more to the cause of good writing than a writer protesting outside it. This is the practical meaning of the thesis, and it is the invitation the paper extends to the colleagues whose condemnation opened it: the room needs you, and your grievance, properly channeled, is a qualification rather than a disqualification.

Public-Interest Technology and Program Design

The umbrella for all of this is the emerging field of public-interest technology, which trains technologists to serve the public the way public-interest law trains lawyers to. Concretely, the program-design implications are several. Doctoral programs should offer dual or joint training structures pairing computer science with a domain or a humanistic discipline. They should embed ethics and the study of documented harms throughout rather than quarantining them. They should provide access to a computer sufficient for meaningful frontier-adjacent work, which implies the public infrastructure discussed in the policy section. They should

reward, in hiring and promotion, the public-interest and exploratory research that industry will not fund, including the maintenance of public datasets, the auditing of deployed systems, and the slow, unglamorous work of validating models against real-world data. And they should actively recruit from the humanities and the professions, treating a writer's, clinician's, or lawyer's expertise as an asset to be combined with technical training rather than a deficit to be overcome.

Part 8. Engagement Without a Doctorate: On-Ramps for Creative Professionals

The paper has so far argued with writers while prescribing to governments, universities, and funders, and that mismatch deserves a direct answer. Engagement does not require a PhD. The professionals initially harmed by AI should be encouraged to be in the room and to be heard, and most of the rooms that matter do not require a doctorate to enter. The writer quoted at the outset can act on the grievance by engaging substantively rather than standing back and calling people names. Non-involvement does not excuse vitriol or willful ignorance, though the non-involvement itself is understandable. This section names concrete on-ramps, each tied to an existing institution or mechanism, so that the invitation extended throughout the paper has a set of doors attached.

The first on-ramp is collective licensing. Judge Chhabria's observation that book rights are too fragmented to license efficiently is not only a description of an obstacle; it is a job posting. Writers' organizations, agents, and publishers can build the collective-licensing infrastructure that does not yet exist, the equivalent for training rights of what performing-rights organizations built for music. A novelist who helps design a licensing collective shapes the terms on which their own work, and their peers' work, is used. That is engagement of the most consequential kind, and it requires craft knowledge of publishing, not a degree in machine learning.

The second on-ramp is advisory and program-design work. Doctoral programs, public-interest technology consortia, and the funders described in the next section need practitioners on their advisory boards and curriculum committees. A working writer who sits on the panel that designs an embedded-ethics curriculum, or who advises a dataset-documentation effort, brings exactly the precise-language discipline the field lacks. These seats exist; they are frequently unfilled for want of practitioners willing to take them.

The third on-ramp is dataset documentation and provenance work. The honest, accountable systems the paper calls for depend on knowing what went into them. Creators are uniquely positioned to contribute to provenance standards, consent registries, and the documentation of training corpora, the unglamorous infrastructure on which licensed use depends. This is paid, concrete, near-term work that does not require building a model.

The fourth on-ramp is participation in auditing and red-teaming panels. The independent auditing institutions the paper recommends will need domain experts, including writers and editors, to evaluate generative systems for harms that only practitioners notice. A translator can spot a translation failure a computer scientist will miss; an editor can identify the precise register in which a model's output curdles into slop. These evaluative judgments are a form of expertise, and the auditing function cannot do without them.

The fifth on-ramp is standards and policy comment. The regulatory frameworks described below evolve through public comment, participation by standards bodies, and testimony. A writer who files a comment on an AI standard, or who testifies about the working conditions of creative labor under automation, is in the room as surely as any researcher. None of these on-ramps requires abandoning the grievance. Each channels it into a venue where it can change an outcome rather than merely register a complaint.

Part 9. Policy and Institutional Implications

Diagnosis without a prescription is incomplete. This section translates the argument into institutional recommendations, and in keeping with the paper's discipline, each recommendation is tied to a benchmark that would indicate success or signal the need for a different approach. The recommendations share a center of gravity: each is a measure to retain public-interest researchers, because the evidence from the pipeline section is that production without retention feeds the capture it is meant to cure.

Public Funding Tied to Public-Interest Agendas

The first recommendation is that public research funding for AI be expanded and explicitly tied to public-interest agendas that industry will not pursue: bias detection and mitigation, clinical validation against real patient data, independent safety and interpretability research, and the study of documented harms. The benchmark is the academic share of notable models and benchmarks, currently in the single-digit to low-double-digit range, and the academic share of new doctorates, which the 2026 AI Index shows is recovering. If public funding is working, the recovery in the share of academic doctorates should continue, and the academic contribution to consequential, non-commercial research should grow. If those shares stagnate or reverse, the funding level or its targeting is inadequate and should change.

Alignment With Regulatory Frameworks

The second recommendation is that doctoral training and public research align with the maturing regulatory frameworks, because researchers will increasingly work inside them. The European Union's AI Act entered into force on August 1, 2024, with its high-risk obligations originally due to apply on August 2, 2026 ([Council of the European Union, 2026](#)). The 2025-

2026 Digital Omnibus simplification process substantially revised this timeline: under a provisional political agreement reached in May 2026 that awaits formal adoption at this writing, the high-risk obligations for stand-alone Annex III systems are deferred to December 2, 2027, and for AI embedded in regulated products under Annex I to August 2, 2028, while a new prohibition on AI-generated non-consensual intimate imagery and child sexual abuse material is added. In the United States, the National Institute of Standards and Technology's AI Risk Management Framework, released in January 2023, has become a reference standard, with subsequent profiles extending it toward critical-infrastructure contexts ([National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2023](#)). The benchmark is whether graduating doctoral researchers are fluent in these frameworks and whether public research demonstrably informs their evolution. If regulators continue to defer obligations for lack of the standards and tools to implement them, as the Omnibus deferral reflects, that is a direct signal that more independent research capacity is needed to build those standards, and funding should follow.

Dual-Appointment Retention Models

The third recommendation addresses the brain drain at its source and is the most direct retention measure among the five. Since universities cannot match industry compensation, they should adopt dual-appointment models that allow researchers to hold simultaneous positions in academia and industry, retaining a foot in the independent, public-interest research community while accessing industry resources and compensation. The benchmark is the rate at which top researchers retain any academic affiliation. The finding by Jurowetzki et al. (2025) that researchers' novelty declines after full transition to industry suggests that partial retention may preserve some of the exploratory capacity that full migration destroys. If dual appointments

become common and the novelty decline moderates, the model is working; if researchers continue to sever academic ties entirely, stronger incentives are required.

Public Compute Provision

The fourth recommendation is the direct remedy for the compute divide: public provision of computational resources to academic researchers, so that frontier-adjacent research does not require an industry affiliation. The National AI Research Resource pilot is the existing vehicle, and its growth to support a large and rising number of projects and students is encouraging ([National Science Foundation, 2024](#)). The benchmark is whether academic researchers can conduct meaningful work at or near the capability frontier, measured by academic representation among notable models and by the scale of models that academic teams can train. If the public compute resource scales and academic frontier participation rises, the investment is justified; if academic models remain an order of magnitude smaller than industry's, the resource is undersized. Codifying and fully funding such a resource on a durable, long-term basis, rather than as a time-limited pilot, should be a legislative priority.

Funding Independent Red-Teaming and Auditing

The fifth recommendation follows from the conflict-of-interest problem in safety research. Public funds should support independent red-teaming and auditing of frontier models by researchers outside the companies that build them. The GTG-1002 disclosure and the threat-intelligence reports show that the companies are presently both the builders and the principal detectors of misuse, a concentration that the public interest cannot rely on indefinitely ([Anthropic, 2025b](#); [Google Threat Intelligence Group, 2025](#)). The benchmark is the existence and capacity of credible independent auditing institutions. If independent auditors can

meaningfully evaluate frontier systems and their findings inform regulation, the function is healthy; if model evaluation remains effectively internal to the developers, public investment in independent capacity must increase.

Part 10. Conclusion

This paper began with an admission that I have been called vile and despicable by fellow writers for working with artificial intelligence and pursuing a doctorate in it. It ends by returning to that grievance because it is the proper test of the argument. If the case for minting new AI doctorates could be made only by dismissing the writers' complaint, it would be a poor case and an arrogant one. The case is stronger than that. It runs not around the grievance but through it, and it is made, in part, by someone who shares the writer's wound, because I publish fiction into the same diluted market they do.

The writers are right about a great deal. They are right that generative AI has flooded the commons with slop, right that models were built by copying creative work at an industrial scale, and right that this has cost real people real income, a cost now visible in employment data and partially vindicated in the courts. The Thomson Reuters ruling rejected a fair-use defense at summary judgment, a holding now before the Third Circuit; the Bartz settlement extracted \$1.5 billion for piracy; Judge Chhabria's opinion in Kadrey supplied authors a path to the market-dilution theory that may eventually prevail. None of these vindications was won by writers avoiding the technology. They were won by people who refused industry's terms and fought, who engaged with the technology closely enough, in court and at the bargaining table, to name the harm in language a court could act on. That is the distinction this paper has insisted on: refusal as litigation and refusal of harm from inside are forms of engagement, and they work; refusal as avoidance is the only one that forfeits the outcome. The grievance, properly channeled,

is not an argument against AI expertise. It is an argument for more of it, of a particular and accountable kind.

The writers are wrong about the remedy when the remedy is avoidance, and the wrongness matters because the stakes are not confined to the creative economy. AI is non-optional: it has reached majority population adoption faster than the internet; it has won a Nobel Prize; it has reached gold-medal standard in mathematics; it is used in 1,451 cleared medical devices; and it is being applied to fusion, materials, weather, and the basic processes of disease. And AI is dual-use: it has been turned, by a state-sponsored group, into the engine of the first largely autonomous cyber-espionage campaign, and it is being built into adaptive malware by hostile governments. In a world with these properties, avoidance is not a moral stand that anyone will respect. It is a forfeiture. The hostile state, the criminal syndicate, and the lone hacker do not pause for the writer's disapproval. The only defense against AI wielded badly is AI understood well, by enough capable and ethically serious people to matter, and every principled avoidance subtracts one defender while the attackers recruit without scruple.

This returns the argument to its frame. The question AI poses is not whether the work gets done; the bubble may burst, the financing may prove circular, the corporate froth may collapse, and the work will get done regardless, because the capabilities are real. The incentives, public and private, benign and malign, are overwhelming. The question is who does it, under whose ethics, and answerable to whom. A pipeline captured by industry, where roughly 70% of new doctorates flow to private firms, where researchers' novelty declines after they migrate, and where the inflow of AI researchers to the United States has fallen by 89% since 2017, cannot answer that question in favor of the public. It will answer it in favor of whoever pays, and whoever pays is not accountable to the patient, the defendant, the citizen, or the writer.

The remedy is to mint and to keep doctoral researchers of a different kind: interdisciplinary, ethics-fluent, domain-embedded, and publicly accountable. The minting and the keeping are inseparable, because the evidence is plain that production alone, in the current structure, simply enlarges the industry's recruiting pool. It is researchers trained to ask whom a system will harm before they build it, embedded deeply enough in medicine or law or governance to anticipate failure, fluent in alignment and interpretability so that the most powerful systems are not the ones marking their own homework, and held in the public-interest community by public funding, public compute, dual appointments, and independent auditing so that the public interest has a research community of its own. And it is, pointedly, humanists and writers inside the room rather than protesting outside it, because the questions AI forces are finally questions of value and language, and those are answered badly when answered only by engineers. There is one encouraging sign that this future is within reach: the academic share of new doctorates has begun, albeit fragilely, to recover. Whether it continues depends on choices not yet made.

To the colleagues who have judged me harshly: your grievance is legitimate, and the room where the uses of this technology are being decided is poorer for your absence. You do not need a doctorate to enter it, only to trade avoidance for engagement, through a licensing collective, an advisory seat, a provenance standard, or a comment on a rule. The technology will be shaped by whoever shows up, and I would rather it were shaped, in part, by writers.

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